

ThetaWin DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7659263

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Graphical user interface for *Theta* applications (Schrausser, 2009) within ConsoleApp_Distribution Functions (Schrausser, 2024), generating distributions and estimators for several parameters θ via *bootstrap* method, with given number of resamples B , where bootstrap estimator

$$\hat{\theta}_B = B^{-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^B \theta_i^*$$

introduced by Efron (1979, 1981, 1982) as a further development of the *Jackknife* method (Quenouille, 1949). See also *Monte-Carlo* Methode (Metropolis & Ulam, 1949) and *permutation or randomization* tests, first mentioned by Fisher (1935), based on his own account of experiments in agriculture (Fisher, 1926) and the work by Neyman (1923).

In this context see further Pitman (1937a, b, 1938), Fisher (1966, 1971), Efron et al. (1992), Good (2006), Edgington and Onghena (2007), Beasley and Rodgers (2009), Oneto (2020) or Kauermann et al. (2021). A fundamental comparative overview of the different methods and approaches is given by Schrausser (1996, 2025, res.).

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